

USE OF BASALT FIBERS IN IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BUILDING MATERIALS AND STRUCTURES

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Abstract: In this article, the production processes of building materials based on industrial waste, the amount of annual industrial waste by industrial enterprises, and the use of basalt fibers in the correction of physical and mechanical properties of building materials and structures. Information about the history of their appearance and use is provided..

Key words: Industrial waste, basalt, basalt fiber, thermal insulation materials, basalt fiber, portland cement, gypsum, light and heavy concretes, high-quality concretes.

It is known that currently, industrial waste is generated in all sectors of production in a very large amount, and the disposal of this waste is one of the main problems of our time. Currently, production without waste separation is one of the most pressing issues.

Currently, there is a mine with a very large basalt stone reserve in the Osmonsoy village of Jizzakh region, and an enterprise that uses this mine to produce various products (reinforcements for construction work, geogrids, rovings) is operating in the region. Although the enterprise has not been operating for a long time, more than 350 tons of basalt fiber waste have accumulated at the enterprise.

Ordinary heavy concrete based on B15 (M200) was prepared by adding 0.9% basalt fiber of the MII-63 brand with a size of 10 mm and compared its compressive strength with the standard.

The effect of adding 10 mm basalt fibers of the MII-63 brand to ordinary heavy concrete based on B15 (M200) cement on the compressive strength of concrete.

Currently, the composition of heavy concrete mixtures includes basalt fiber with a length of 5-20 mm; 0.5%; 0.7%; 0.9%; compared to the mass of white cement, samples with basalt fiber were prepared by adding basalt fiber to the samples, and initial positive results were obtained during the testing of samples with basalt fiber.

When a sample prepared from the obtained 10x10x10 cm concrete samples was tested in a hydraulic press, samples prepared without additives, 3, 7 and 28-day samples prepared with the addition of 0.9% basalt fiber with a length of 10 mm, showed positive results. Due to the strong bonding of basalt fibers with concrete, the tensile strength of concrete increases by 50...60%, fracture toughness and durability, as well as other properties are significantly improved. Ordinary heavy concretes based on basalt fibers have high fracture toughness, tensile strength, and abrasion resistance.

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